

TRAIN4EU

Transforming ReseArch & INnovation
agendas and support in 4EU+

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Description of the deliverable

Deliverable title: D 7.5 PUBLICATIONS ON LESSONS LEARNED AND BEST PRACTICES

Work Package: WP 7 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication [Month 1-36] led by University of Copenhagen

Deliverable 7.5 *Publications on lessons learned and best practices, as well as policy briefs on R&I transformations aimed at internal and external decision makers within education and research sectors (based on deliverables from WP1-6)* covers the main lessons learned, best practices and key-take aways from TRAIN4EU in terms of published and publicly disseminated outcomes.

D7.5 provides an overview of lessons learned and best practices regarding the R&I support domains articulated in the SwafS 32-call transformation modules coming out of TRAIN4EU during the full project period January 2021 to December 2023 (M1-36). It includes short descriptions of the two ERA policy briefs submitted as D7.6 (M18) and D7.7 (M36).

For a full overview of dissemination of activities and outcomes from TRAIN4EU through various channels, please refer to D7.4 *Documentation of Dissemination of Project Results* (M36).

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Main learnings and project progress

In September 2023, all SwafS projects were asked by REA to provide an update on the [Progress of University Alliances projects](#) report covering good practices in the transformation modules (TMs) of both pilot I and pilot II projects, published Spring 2023. In terms of scope, REA, together with DG RTD and external experts, is working on several reports highlighting best practices that could further inspire policies and support actions. The aim of the update was to ensure that the reports take into account the latest updates of the SwafS projects' results.

REA requested updates on good practices across the TMs addressed in TRAIN4EU, besides those highlighted in Periodic Review Report 1 (Aug. 2022). TRAIN4EU addresses all 7 suggested TMs in the H2020 SwafS 31-32 call through WP1-6. The overview of updates on progress in WP1-6 in reporting period 2 (M19-36) outlined below is adapted from the feedback report sent to REA on 29. Sept. 2023.

TM 1. Developing Common R&I Agenda – WP 1 / lead University of Milan (UM)

Scope: In reporting period 2, WP 1 continued to map out current best practices and identified options for transformative improvement in work ways to enhance shared research agendas within universities. The aim is to design innovative transformative actions towards the development of a common and sustainable research agenda. Topical subtasks addressed included:

- a) *Co-designing pilot transformative actions:* A first pilot action Net4Res was implemented on 8. Nov. 2022: an online informative and networking meeting addressed to all 4EU+ researchers, with focus on HE funding opportunities related to sustainability. Based on the outcome of this pilot action, a second phase of co-designing of pilot actions was planned to improve their impact and efficacy, using both positive and negative lessons learned from previous WP 1 tasks, analyses and ideas for co-designing and perfecting pilot transformative actions.
- b) *Stakeholder consultations:* WP1 participated in two physical meetings in Italy in collaboration with European University Alliances: Univ. of Palermo 21 Feb. 2022 and Bocconi Univ. 25 May 2023. The meetings provided inspiration for innovative actions and exchanges of experiences and ideas among Alliances. WP1 was also present at the Annual EARMA Conference in Prague (24-26 April 2023), with further chances to exchange and reflect on the design of pilot actions.
- c) *Innovations and learning-driven transformations:* based on the assessment of WP 1 activities, WP 1 will identify a set of innovations and learning-driven transformations suitable for upscaling across the alliance, and with the potential of other European universities exploiting the outcomes. Among these, we will select those suitable for potential piloting.

TM 2. Sharing Research Infrastructures – WP 3 / lead University of Heidelberg (UHD)

Scope: In reporting period 2, WP 3 searched for promising models for sharing infrastructures across research groups and explored possibilities for joint utilisation of core facilities. An inventory and categorization of physical research infrastructure across 4EU+ was created and best practices for management, as well as potential barriers for utilising, sharing and scaling infrastructure investments, identified. Topical subtasks addressed included:

- a) *Best practices:* Potential best practices for strengthened competences and on-the-job development of the research infrastructure technical support staff, and the centralised research support units, were identified.
- b) *Co-learning effort across all six universities:* WP3 analyses were supported through a series of online and physical meetings, where ideas for new innovative approaches to management and support for technical infrastructure and support services were shared. A new category for Core Facilities support staff was identified, which could be implemented at all European Universities. Findings will be published in a working paper; see below for more details.

- c) *Consultations with selected stakeholders*: Ongoing consultations with stakeholders across partner countries to overcome obstacles for shared infrastructure development and sustainable Core Facility management. Potential barriers to staff development and joint utilization of Core Facilities, located on management and funding level, were found.
- d) *Innovations and learning-driven transformations*: Based on our assessment, potentials for innovations and learning-driven transformations suitable for upscaling across the alliance, and with the potential of exploitation by other European Universities, have been identified.

TM 3. Strengthening Human Capital – WP 2 / lead Charles University, Prague (CU)

Scope: In reporting period 2, WP 2 focused on activities and outcomes in terms of transformative change potential and piloting of Strengthening Management of R&I Human Capital. While further EU funding (under WIDERA) was not secured, there is a strong commitment to continue outcomes such as enhancing work-life balance and staff exchanges. Potential pilot actions identified will be pursued through alternative funding or institutional support. Topical subtasks addressed included:

- a) *Attracting and retaining talents at all career stages*: focus on learning about promotion programs, training schemes, and strategies for recruiting, welcoming, and supporting newcomers to our universities. CU aims to adopt part of UCPH's promotion program.
- b) *Welcome centers*: Amid the ongoing crisis of the war in Ukraine, welcome centers are experiencing heightened demand to accommodate Ukrainian researchers and students in search of safety. Best practices have been exchanged, encompassing financial aid, language courses, psychological support, and contract extensions for Ukrainian researchers. As the conflict persists and needs evolve, WP2 remains committed to sharing best practices.
- c) *Performance and development review*: Best practices of UCPH Performance & Development Review scheme for early-stage (R1) and mid-level researchers (R2), as well as their managers were exchanged among partners for mutual learning. Several institutions are considering pilot programs inspired by UCPH's scheme; UW is actively working on implementation.
- d) *Gender Equality*: Plans to develop a comprehensive set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), both quantitative and qualitative, aimed at assessing the gender equality gap in academia will not be fully realized within the project timeframe due to insufficient data.

TM 4. Engaging Non-Academic Actors – WP 4 / lead Sorbonne University Paris (SU)

TM 6. Citizen and Societal Engagement – WP 4 / lead Sorbonne University Paris (SU)

Scope: In reporting period 2, WP 4 addressed Academia-Business-Citizens links through a cross-over learning effort and a series of online and physical meetings with all 4eu+ Alliance universities and selected stakeholders. Pilot actions have been identified to gather and disseminate inspiration for transformative actions to bring university innovation to society. Topical subtasks addressed included:

- a) *Co-learning effort, sharing analyses*: TRAINER is developing a "network of experts" around valorisation and transfer to address possible points of connection beyond local and national contexts. Three topics were selected based on co-learning methods and sharing analyses: Transfer for SSH and non-commercial knowledge transfer; Developing and adapting training for young and senior researchers and raising awareness of researchers and supporting the creation of start-ups; Improving relations between researchers and companies.
- b) *Set of learning-driven actions*: Three pilot actions suitable for up-scaling across 4eu+ were discussed in the final project phase, based on co-learning efforts & sharing analysis, to assess the possibility of carrying out this type of action on a regular basis at the 4eu+ Alliance level.
- c) *Consultations with selected stakeholders*: ongoing consultations with selected stakeholders in partner countries to gather and promote inspiration for innovative and transformative

actions to bring university innovation into society. Sorbonne University hosted a webinar on 27. Nov. 2023 with representatives of 4eu+, industrial stakeholders, innovation ecosystems partners and the European Commission to present successful innovation achievements across the 4eu+ Alliance and engage the community into long term objectives; see below.

TM 5. Mainstreaming Open Science – WP 5 / lead University of Warsaw (UW)

Scope: In reporting period 2, WP 5 focused on university libraries and other university units which can play a significant role in promoting and facilitating Open Science. How such units can support openness in practice for researchers, even if there are no institutional solutions to promote it, was explored, including the specialist knowledge required for advising on publishing and/or preparing research data management plans. Topical subtasks addressed included:

- a) *Research Data Management and FAIR Data:* in relation to open research data, RDM support services, RDM activities and data stewardship, RDM trainings and data repositories have been analyzed, with recommendations on RDM services, RDM job profiles, RDM trainings and on data repositories included in the final report D5.3 (M35).
- b) *Responsible publishing:* Open access publishing in 4eu+ in 2021-2022 was analyzed and the number of publications, subject areas, types of open access and ratio of open publications to total number of publications, funding sponsors, publishers and co-publication outlined.
- c) *Citizen science:* Citizen science projects and skills and funding in CS projects were analyzed, and recommendations formulated on support, infrastructures and funding model for CS projects as well as suggestions how 4eu+ can expand its collaboration and focus on CS.
- d) *Toolkits for Open Science advocacy:* Toolkits were prepared as an integrated part of WP 5 task 3, with the aim to make them a permanent achievement of the project, by launching them as a pilot action in the Alliance's partner universities and beyond; see D5.3 (M35).

TM 7. Exploring Joint University Structures – WP 6 / lead University of Copenhagen (UCPH)

Scope: In reporting period 2, WP 6 continued efforts to facilitate inter-alliance collaboration in R&I support functions, in order to develop a sustainable governance for joint collaboration within 4eu+ and across European University Alliances. Topical subtasks addressed included:

- a) *Collaboration on R&I support:* Ongoing focus on collaborations in 4eu+ and with European University Alliances on sharing best practice and known drivers of success. Explorations on barriers to collaboration and identification of potential mechanisms that can circumvent or minimise the effect of barriers on implementing transformation of R&I support functions.
- b) *Joint learning processes:* Ongoing focus on activities and outcomes in terms of joint learning processes include coordination of and participation in activities such as webinars and other forms of exchanges on R&I support, to ensure joint learning across 4eu+ and other alliances.
- c) *SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023* in Bruxelles on 30. Nov.-1. Dec. 2023 brought European Commission officials and members of European University Alliances together to discuss the future of research & innovation dimensions within alliances and to showcase best practices and lessons learned from the SwafS pilot projects; see more detailed description below.

Publications on lessons learned and best practices

Below please find some highlights from TRAIN4EU in terms of published lessons learned and best practices. More events, news and dissemination activities can be found on [TRAIN4EU's website](#).

4eu+ Conference on Educational and Research infrastructure collaboration

On 8. June 2022, University of Copenhagen coordinated the **4eu+ On-line Conference on Educational and Research infrastructure collaboration in European University Alliances**, under the auspices of TRAIN4EU WP6 *Governance for Joint Collaboration*. Its scope was to cover both R&I and education dimensions of infrastructure, and explore their interfaces, to create synergy and strengthen the integration of the two core university dimensions. It was a joint event involving TRAIN4EU, with WP 3 *Sharing Research Infrastructure* as the main focal point, and 4eu+'s Erasmus+ funded EUP project.

The following text is from an article published in the June 2022 4eu+ newsletter and 4eu+ website:

The 4EU+ conference held on 8 June showed the pressing need for collaboration within educational and research infrastructure.

4EU+ Conference: Learnings, challenges and obstacles in educational and research infrastructure

We should keep building on what is already there. The 4EU+ conference held on 8 June showed the pressing need for collaboration within educational and research infrastructure. Participants expressed their readiness to do so – collaborating across differences and similarities.

Representatives and practitioners of 4EU+, EUGLOH, Una Europa, CIVIS, CHARM-EU, EPICUR University Alliance and the European Commission shared and discussed experiences, challenges and best practices when they met online at the 4EU+ infrastructure conference on 8 June 2022.

Distinguished speakers Deputy Head of Unit at the European Commission Tine Delva from DG EAC and Head of Sector Research Infrastructures Agnes Robin from DG RTD, as well as 4EU+ speakers Professors Sabine Bottin-Rousseau from Sorbonne University and Bo Jellesmark Thorsen from University of Copenhagen, kicked off the 4EU+ Conference on Educational and Research Infrastructure Collaboration in European University Alliances, sharing insights on infrastructure collaborations and discussed potentials for transformative actions.

Interconnection and digitalization in education

A focal point for the educational infrastructure was to keep developing an appropriate infrastructure that does not leave people behind. To do so we need to be connected digitally and balance our educational needs between physical and digital. Our systems must be interconnected – and we need to strive to make universities connected, said Tine Delva, Deputy Head of Unit Higher Education, DG EAC. She pointed out all the pioneering work that is going on and which will keep the ball rolling even though we are challenged by different levels of maturity at the individual universities.

In the parallel sessions on educational infrastructure participants identified that we have many of the same challenges and use cases, but we don't need to use the same systems. Several speakers noted that collaboration between Alliances to ensure interoperability of systems would be key to achieving interconnectedness. The integration of new innovative technological pedagogical tools

with the use of emerging technologies such as AI in LMSs and the development of quality assessment tools are also underway. Further, challenges of creating common infrastructure goes beyond IT systems. The current regulatory barriers also need to be addressed.

In the words of Sabine Bottin-Roussau, coordinator of the 4EU+ European University Project: “Infrastructure is essential to the materialisation of our activities as it represents the campuses of our Alliances. It must facilitate our communication, both for internal cooperation within our alliance and externally, not only for teachers, researchers, students, but also for our staff, and ultimately, all organisations involved in our universities.”

Through the exchanges that took place in the parallel sessions, participants from across Alliances were able to identify a common and strong ambition and will to work with open solutions and standards, and to keep better control over the data.

Drawing the insights on educational infrastructure together 3 questions to be jointly addressed by Alliances can be formulated:

- With all these developments in the different alliances, we are at a critical point where we have to cooperate. Are we ready to go beyond sharing and start collaborating?
- Legal issue regarding GDPR and safe data exchange during mobilities requires a strong agreement within the universities. Can we find a way to share our students' data within our alliances to facilitate all processes?
- Finally, will the next phase allow us to think about virtual academic development and the possibility of providing training tools for students and teachers to address the issue of digital transition and inclusiveness when offering blended and hybrid learning?

Building on experiences and adapting to needs

Infrastructure is strategic to all at Higher Education Institutions, be they teachers, researchers or students. Agnès Robin, Head of Sector Research Infrastructures at the European Commission, highlighted the [20 actions of the ERA Policy Agenda](#), especially action number eight about strengthening sustainability, accessibility and resilience of research infrastructures.

We should keep in mind, several speakers noted, that we don't need to start from scratch but rather build on our many experiences and existing initiatives when it comes to a pan-European infrastructure: In the last 20 years we have developed a much more interconnected landscape with many ongoing activities and experiences that we can build on and adapt to our needs to make the best of our resources. The overall conclusion was that we need to align - not to invent a new and perfect solution. And we need to continue the work with the support of the EU Commission. This is in particular a statement that addresses the larger pan-European collaborations on larger infrastructures. The Alliances though, all had their focus on the many smaller to fairly large infrastructures they rarely share even across universities - or faculties for that matter.

The importance of an inclusive research infrastructure definition

In the parallel session on research infrastructure it was stressed that the definition of research infrastructure should be inclusive: infrastructure is more than core facilities and technical tools. It's also social sciences, humanities and interdisciplinary facilities. And we need to open infrastructure and give access to citizens and businesses so we can share knowledge in new collaborative ways.

[UNITECH](#) was highlighted as a best practice case within research infrastructure at the University of Milan. Professor Gabriella Tedeschi presented the system in place for sharing four fairly large

infrastructures at University of Milan, including a detailed schedule for fees and access rights. She stressed that UNITECH can be upscaled to offer services across the European University Alliances.

‘We have a solid experience in collaboration on pan-European infrastructures. However, universities spend massive funds on smaller and medium infrastructures. This seminar presented different innovative approaches to enhancing the management and sharing of these to increase the value for the entire ERA. While these efforts will undoubtedly improve management, we also identified forthcoming challenges and open questions’, says Bo Jellesmark, TRAIN4EU+ coordinator from University of Copenhagen, pointing out three questions:

As universities seek to engage actively with innovation efforts and the private sector, we need to ask ourselves if further innovations in how we manage and share research infrastructures will be called for?

We may also ask ourselves if we can design systems for sharing and managing infrastructure sufficiently transparent for them to actually further and ease the interaction between university research groups and private sector actors?

The fundamentals of Open Science will require us to develop better infrastructure for data storage, management and access, and we need to ask ourselves if we pay enough attention to these?

During the parallel sessions it was mentioned that there is a need for joint learning for managers and technical-scientific staff of identical or closely related research infrastructures. On a European level, there is common focus on countries jointly developing, operating and paying for costly, largescale research infrastructures within scientific organizations such as CERN, ESA, ESO, ITER, EMBL, ESS etc. These organizations each hire and train their own staff. Inside the larger European scientific organizations, there is also a career-path. However, some would say that on the European level there is much less focus, if any, on the training of technical and scientific staff who at university level are operating medium and smaller size research. During the parallel session on the conference it was discussed that a focus on this group of staff and their know-how through network-building and seed funding could greatly enhance the development of research infrastructures in Europe.

Intensifying collaboration between Alliances

In the concluding plenary reflections participants agreed on the necessity of inter-alliance collaboration to provide the interoperability that is essential to deliver on the ambition of European Universities.

More about the event, including key messages and questions, recordings of the plenary sessions and the conference programme can be found on the [TRAIN4EU website](#).

233 participants registered for the conference, of which approx. 150 participating consistently for 3 hours, and 110 participating for 4 hours. Participants were evenly distributed in education and research parallel sessions. Registered participants included 207 participants from a European University Alliance, of which 106 participants were from 4eu+, 21 participants were private participants / other affiliations, and 5 participants were from the European Commission.

Working paper on sharing research infrastructures

As outlined in D5.3 (M35), WP3 participants jointly wrote the working paper “*Navigating the Frontier: Research Infrastructures, Core Facilities and the Shaping of a New Paradigm at European Universities*”. The paper, with all WP participants listed as authors, was submitted to the [European Management Journal](#) in August 2023 and the [European Journal of Innovation Management](#) in September 2023. Both journals rejected the article due to scope misfit. In October 2023, the paper was submitted to the [Journal of Education Policy](#), where it is currently with the Editor. If not accepted by this journal, it is planned to publish the paper within the 4EU+ network by the end of 2023. The paper abstract reads:

Research Infrastructures (RI) and Core Facilities (CF) are strong drivers for generating research results and, thus, knowledge at European Universities. In this paper, we provide insight into different features of RI and CF, their organisational structure and governance, funding mechanisms, critical factors for success, and challenges and opportunities associated with implementing and operating these research support structures. Our results are based on a comparative analysis across six European research-intensive universities from the 4EU+ University Alliance. Due to the lack of a clear definition of RI and CF, we provide a variety of indicators and criteria attributed to such facilities. We highlight differences between CF and RI in terms of goals and objectives. Establishing Core Facilities can be seen as a response to the evolving needs and challenges of researchers and academic communities at European Universities. With a centralised management and collaborative governance model, Core Facilities provide a practical solution to address these needs. We explore the legal framework, organisation, access, users and charge rate models at Core Facilities. We also identify several challenges in setting up and maintaining Core Facilities. Special attention is directed towards staff challenges, including introducing the staff category we identify as “scientific technical experts”. Finally, we present a Core Facility Manifesto and share our conclusions.

The paper seeks to highlight the features of research infrastructure and particularly of Core Facilities, and to demonstrate the challenges many facilities face when dealing with recognition and criteria for incorporation in the research framework of universities and other higher education institutions (HEI). Especially issues of sustainable funding and the challenge of long-term perspectives for infrastructure staff, who the authors refer to as “scientific technical experts”, pose serious obstacles for fostering infrastructure development. These issues, among others, are addressed in the paper.

Webinar on transfer from academia to business and society

Sorbonne University organized and hosted a webinar under the auspices of WP4 *Linking citizens-academia-business*, focusing on collaboration between universities, industry and society.

The text below is from an article published in the December 2023 4eu+ newsletter and on the [4eu+ website](#), where further information can be found:

TRAIN4EU+ Webinar: Transfer from academia to business and society

On 27th November 2023, TRAIN4EU+ hosted a webinar entitled 'Transfer from academia to business and society'. The webinar, organized and hosted by Sorbonne University TRAIN4EU+ and 4EU+ local team, gathered high level representatives from 4EU+ member universities, European Commission officials, valuable socio-economic partners and 50+ participants from across the consortium.

The webinar aimed to demonstrate the effectiveness of collaboration and successful interactions between academia, the business sector, and society. It also offered thematic discussions on this transfer process, specifically on SSH transfer, entrepreneurship training and relations with SME's. Focal areas included:

- A dedicated session highlighting successful transitions from academia to business within 4EU+ member universities.
- Distinguished speakers offering nuanced perspectives and in-depth insights on academic-business transfers, including a focus on social sciences and humanities (SSH), entrepreneurship education, and productive collaborations with small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

[Please consult the entire program for the event >>>](#)

The successful event provided empirical evidence and qualitative assessments of transfer from academia to business and society, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the symbiotic relationship between academia and business. The event also served to boost a reinforced deployment of the research and innovation axis of the 4EU+Alliance.

“ We still have to develop and to promote the networks within the Alliance .. [with the idea] to use the 4EU+ Alliance to upscale transfer research at the European level [...] and to make it more efficient” Prof. Guillaume Fiquet - Sorbonne Université - Vice-Rector International affairs

Key take-aways and outputs:

- **Success stories:** the event showcased multiple success stories and case studies illustrating successful academia-to-business transfers within 4EU+ member universities. These examples provided practical insights into effective collaborations and strategies utilized in the transfers.
- **Guidelines & policies:** the discussions in the thematic approaches session may contribute to the development of frameworks or guidelines aimed at enhancing academia-business collaboration. These frameworks could include recommendations for smoother knowledge transfer and improved interaction models such as joint doctoral networks. Insights from the event could also be used to influence the development of policies or programs at different levels to promote stronger ties between academia, business, and society.
- **Increased Awareness:** Sharing success stories and discussing collaborations through various channels contributes to raising awareness about the importance of academia-business partnerships. This increased visibility will help attract more interest and boost participation in future initiatives.

SwafS Cross Alliances Forum 2023

TRAIN4EU was part of the organizing committee for the SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 in Bruxelles on 30. November-1. December 2023. WP6 lead and TRAIN4EU project manager Miriam Koktvedgaard Zeitzen worked on the event under the auspices of WP6 *Governance for Joint Collaboration*, which focuses on strengthening collaboration across alliances.

The following text is from an article published in the December 2023 4eu+newsletter and on the [4eu+ website](#), where further information can be found:

SwafS conference: Science with and for Society in European University Alliances

During the 1½ day SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 in Bruxelles on 30. November-1. December 2023, European Commission officials met with members of the European University Alliances to discuss the future of the research & innovation dimension within university alliances in Europe and to showcase best practices and lessons learned from the Horizon2020-funded SwafS projects.

With more than 200 participants, the Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 was buzzing with energy from members of the 32 participating alliances as well as the many external stakeholders – with European Commission representatives actively engaged in the lively discussion about research and innovation in the European University Alliances. Challenges encountered by the alliances were discussed and a variety of recommendations and lessons learned were presented during the conference.

4eu+ was part of the organizing committee of the event, which was coordinated by CHARM-EU. Work on the event formed part of TRAIN4EU+ Work Package (WP) 6 *Governance for Joint Collaboration*, led by project manager Miriam Koktvedgaard Zeitzen. WP 6 focuses on sharing lessons learned and exchanging best practices coming out of 4eu+'s SwafS project TRAIN4EU+, to upscale collaboration in research support functions across 4eu+ and European University Alliances.

From Agenda Setting to Implementation

TRAIN4EU+'s main intervention was in the panel *'From Agenda Setting to Implementation: Maximizing the Institutional Impact of the SwafS Projects'* on Day 1, which was co-organised by 4eu+ and FORTHEM. Panelists from five European University Alliances provide insights into challenges and successes in implementing their SwafS projects, with a focus on achieving lasting institutional impact within alliances.

TRAIN4EU+ coordinator and Prorector for Research at University of Copenhagen, David Dreyer Lassen, spoke on the challenges but also the benefits of sharing research infrastructures within alliances. Focal points included the need for flexible models for sharing research infrastructure that respect national legislation, contractual obligations and other requirements, and that still enable a culture of sharing.

Topics raised within the panel included the challenge in developing joint structures for research & innovation (R&I) in universities with a very long institutional history and very diverse infrastructures. The importance of developing joint PhD programmes in transdisciplinary fields was also discussed. This will enable early-stage researchers to be mobile and open to various cultures of doing research. And it will give them a chance to use various facilities and infrastructures of partner universities.

A main challenge addressed by the panel was how the alliances can move forward without a solid, flexible and targeted budget to implement and further develop the results from the SwafS-projects. Solutions include investment pathways and strategies to maximize impact of the work done so far.

What are the SwafS projects leaving for the future?

Workshop 2 on Day 1, organized by 4eu+, focused on *Pilots and Action Plans: what are the SwafS projects leaving for future developments of the Alliances' R&I dimension*. Speaking on behalf of 4eu+ was Ladislav Kristoufek, CU Vice Rector Research. The workshop was moderated by 4eu+ policy officer Elena del Giorgio, University of Milan.

A main recommendation was the need to strengthen the SwafS projects' efforts to position European University Alliances as key contributors to the European R&I landscape. One approach is highlighting the alliances' unique value in complement to existing R&I collaborations. A further

recommendation was advocating for future funding and investment to allow European University Alliances to take forward their ambitions and fulfil their potential as drivers of the European Research Area, in Europe as well as globally.

The roles of research managers and research support officers in addressing challenges of the alliances in terms of research support functions covered by the SwafS projects were also discussed. One such challenge is the outsourcing of proposal writing to external consultants by some universities.

Best practices in poster session

32 alliances' examples on best practices and outcomes of their R&I SwafS projects were showcased in an interactive poster session on Day 1, organized around the seven transformational modules in the SwafS call.

[All the highlights from the poster session are to be found here including links to every poster.](#)

Representing TRAIN4EU+, Anne Jürgens from Heidelberg University, leader of WP 3 *Sharing research infrastructure*, presented project learnings on how to facilitate sharing of core facilities across universities and borders – a relevant topic not only for life sciences and natural sciences but also for humanities and social sciences. UNITECH Core Facilities at the University of Milan was highlighted as 4eu+ best practice.

Publish or Perish in the age of Artificial Intelligence

TRAIN4EU+'s final intervention at the SwafS Cross-Alliances Forum 2023 was in Roundtable 2 on Day 2, which focused on *Research Ethics & Integrity: The Role of New Technologies*. The 4eu+ speaker was once again CU Vice Rector Research Ladislav Kristoufek, who gave a spirited talk on 'Publish or Perish in the age of AI.' EC approaches to AI in research were also presented and discussed at the roundtable.

The SwafS conference ended with a closing session, one portion of which was dedicated to a recap of all the workshops and roundtables during the event. On behalf of 4eu+, Elena del Giorgio summed up some of the key takeaways that came out of Workshop 2 on SwafS pilots and action plans.

All in all the event was very successful in disseminating best practices and lessons learned from the Horizon2020-funded SwafS projects, as well as providing rich opportunities to network and exchange with other European University Alliances, and with representatives from DG EAC and DG RTD as well as REA.

For a fuller description of the event programme, please see [CHARM-EUs website](#). For a final report on the learnings from the SwafS Forum, please see [CHARM-EUs website](#).

Please Annex 1 and 2 for summaries and learnings from the SwafS Forum sessions which TRAIN4EU lead or co-lead: Day 1 Panel Session and Workshop 2. The rapports from the two sessions will form part of the final report from the SwafS Forum, to be published by CHARM-EU on the [SwafS website](#).

ERA Policy Briefs

Policy Brief 1 D7.6

Deliverable 7.6 Policy brief 1 (M18) was the main exploitation activity in TRAIN4EU in DEC Phase II (July 2021 – December 2022; see D7.3 DEC 2nd update (M35)). With the completion of Milestone 5 *Meeting with other alliances*, in the form of the 4eu+ infrastructure conference held on 8. June 2022 (see above), as well as the completion of tasks 1.2 – 4.2 in WP 1-4, shared insights and lessons learned were harnessed to formulate TRAIN4EU's first Policy Brief. Work on Policy Brief 1 included consideration of WP maturity, instruments ready to be rolled out; 4eu+ internal and external stakeholder interest; as well as the strategic focus of 4eu+ & DG RTD.

As indicated in D 7.6, TRAIN4EU is committed to develop a framework for facilitating collaboration on, and possible implementation of, future institutional transformations of selected R&I support functions within 4eu+, as well as across and beyond European University Alliances. TRAIN4EU's policy recommendations are partly inspired by the mapping of cases selected for best practice assessment and innovations, which were in the process of being analysed and potentially piloted in the project and framed within the Horizon2020 SwafS-32 call Transformation Modules.

Policy dialogue meetings with the European Commission. Developing policy advice for policy makers is envisioned as one of TRAIN4EU's main avenues of exploitation to maximise impact. Other avenues include piloting transformative processes and disseminating to other alliances and EU universities. To ensure constructive interface with the ERA policy agenda, as requested in the ERA policy brief template furnished by the EC, a series of meetings with the EC were held to discuss the brief. A multilateral on-line meeting in FOREU1 R&I subgroup was held on 10. Feb. 2022, where DG RTD & REA representatives presented and discussed the new ERA policy brief template with the alliances. Two bilateral meetings between TRAIN4EU, TRAIN4EU PO Marta Truco-Calbet and DG RTD policy officer Stijn Delauré were held: on-line 14. March 2022 and in-person on 31. May 2022 at DG RTD in Bruxelles, to clarify and discuss scope, audience, aims and exploitation of policy recommendations.

Dissemination efforts. Policy Brief 1 forms part of TRAIN4EU's DEC efforts, and while technically submitted within TRAIN4EU WP 7, the brief was framed as a 4eu+ action, to reach a wide audience. Before submission, approval of Policy Brief 1 was therefore obtained from both TRAIN4EU Steering Committee and 4eu+ Management Committee, to ensure alignment with 4eu+ strategy. Audience targets for the brief was 4eu+ internal and external stakeholders, incl. business sectors and civic society; local, regional, national and European level policymakers; 1st & 2nd generation European University Alliances; decision makers in R&I, incl. European Commission (DG RTD & DG EAC).

For content of the ERA policy brief 1, please refer to D7.6 (M18).

Policy Brief 2 D7.7

Deliverable 7.7 Policy brief 2 (M36) was the main exploitation activity in TRAIN4EU DEC Phase III (January 2023 – Dec. 2023; see D7.3 DEC 2nd update (M35)). With the completion of Milestone 7 *Status on collaboration with other alliances*, in the form of the SwafS Cross Alliances Forum 2023 held on 30. Nov. – 1. Dec. 2023 in Bruxelles (see D6.2 (M35) and above), as well as the completion of WP 1-6 tasks 1.3 – 6.2 (see D1.3-6.2 (M35)), shared insights and lessons learned were harnessed to formulate TRAIN4EU's second Policy Brief. Considerations included 4eu+ internal and external

stakeholder interest, strategic focus of 4eu+ & DG RTD, as well as reflections on funding and investment pathways toward sustainable support for the alliances' R&I dimensions.

As indicated in D7.6 Policy Brief 1 (M18), TRAIN4EU is committed to develop a framework for facilitating collaboration on, and possible implementation of, future institutional transformations of selected R&I support functions within 4eu+, as well as across and beyond European University Alliances. TRAIN4EU's policy recommendations are partly inspired by WP1-5 cases selected for best practice assessment and potential implementations as articulated within the Horizon2020 SwafS-32 call TMs. Developing policy advice for policy makers is envisioned as one of TRAIN4EU's main avenues of exploitation to maximise impact for project outcomes. Other avenues include piloting transformative processes and disseminating to other alliances and EU universities.

Dissemination efforts. Policy Brief 2 forms part of TRAIN4EU's DEC efforts, and while technically submitted within TRAIN4EU WP 7, the brief was framed as a 4eu+ action, to reach a wide audience. Approval of Policy Brief 2 was therefore obtained from the 4eu+ Management Committee before submission to ensure alignment with 4eu+ strategy 2025-2035 currently under development. Audience targets are 4eu+ internal and external stakeholders, incl. local, national and European level policymakers, 1st & 2nd generation European University Alliances and the European Commission.

For content of the ERA policy brief 2, please refer to D7.7 (M36).

Annexes

Annex 1: SwafS Forum 2023 Day 1 Panel Session – rapporteur summary

Rapporteur name	Agnese Rusakova
Rapporteur email	agnese.rusakova@lu.lv
Session name	Panel session From Agenda Setting to Implementation: Maximizing the Institutional Impact of the SwafS Projects
Date and time	November, 30, 2023 11:30-12:30
Session abstract	<p>European University alliances have made an impressive step forward to foster collaboration in the research, innovation and transfer dimension. Due to their SwafS projects, alliances embarked on setting up joint R&I agendas and actions plans, and exchanged on best practices, developing tools and structures to facilitate cooperation and bringing researchers together for joint project applications. Taking the next step from setting the agendas to sustainably implementing new formats and activities modelled and tested in the pilot phase requires time and resources. Some alliances have built on their pre-existing joint collaboration before formally establishing the alliance. Other alliances need more time, especially within the research mission, to harmonize their diverse R&I priorities, support structures, internal work flows, policies and resources available. In this session we want representatives of five alliances to talk about their experiences of implementation of the actions planned within their SwafS projects. They will share some examples of how to maximize institutional impacts, despite not having a guarantee of continued funding. And they will show us how the planned actions can promote an integrative approach to all the missions of the university.</p>
Chair name:	Katarzyna Molek-Kozakowska (FORTHEM/FIT FORTHEM)
Speaker name (1):	Siobhan Moane (RUN-EU/ RUN-EU PLUS)
Summary of speaker content (1):	<p>The RUN-EU is a network focused on regional universities.</p> <p>1. The RUN-EU PLUS project is led by TUS: Midlands Midwest and primarily focuses on enhancing the development of R&I with and for society through the development and deployment of collaborative professional practice-based research degrees across the RUN-EU alliance. The main objectives of the project include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a common R&I agenda and associated collaborative action plan focused on the strengthening of regional business and society partnerships in R&I across the network which will complement the existing RUN-EU strategic vision for teaching, learning, research and engagement activities, delivering institutional and societal transformation. Collaboration with regional partners is very important to identify core skills needed for the labour force of the future, we work with companies to understand which skills are needed and translate them further integrating in the content • design and delivery of joint and collaborative accredited professional practice-based research programmes at both masters and PhD level

	<p>across the RUN-EU alliance in association with industry, business, and societal stakeholders and organized around a challenge they face.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • development and implementation of strategies which enhance the capacity of the human capital engaged in research and innovation, through the development of a collaborative cloud of knowledge portal, that amasses training material and disseminates research achievements. • mainstreaming of Open Science practices and skills within the RUN-EU R&I platforms, through the delivery of new and innovative programmes. • contribution to the development of the recently announced ERA Hubs by supporting joint R&I activities across the alliance. For example, get the early stage researchers or senior researchers together for a week and work on a challenge of the week (learn new cultures of doing research), and then present the idea at the end of the week <p>2. An example of how projects like the SwafS-projects can really be institutional game-changers: We have worked on collaborative research degrees at PhD level through either joint supervision leading to a single award or joint award allows progression to PhD for students from institutions which do not have PhD awarding authority and for the institutions themselves. Such cooperation can help to recognize viable career opportunities, develop frameworks that support the transfer of knowledge, like ambassador networks in RIT.</p> <p>3. RUN-EU PLUS has developed such collaborative PhD programmes in the areas of sustainability, digitalisation and social innovation with joint supervision and student mobility integrated into the programmes. An application was submitted to a national education agency for approval of a joint PhD in Digitalisation Engineering between 3 RUN-EU partners. This programme was co-designed by the partners and the taught modules will be co-delivered. Joint supervision (3-4 supervisors from partner universities – there are supervisor training programs and workshops for supervision teams) and mobility are core elements and the application was supported by over 20 companies who will be collaborating on the research carried out. If successful, this PhD will be the first awarded by 2 of the proposing partners.</p>
Speaker name (2):	David Dreyer Lassen (4EU+/TRAIN4EU+)
Summary of speaker content (2):	<p>Sharing research infrastructure, alleviating access to it can be used as tool for attracting talent in a targeted way. It is important to share the good and bad experiences alike. Sharing infrastructure is also fulfilling an important societal role, for example - startups have no access to own infrastructure and can be supported. Even at the individual university level it is difficult to keep on track of developments related to the available infrastructure, what is working, what is available, what is not being repurposed. At the alliance level we need to come up with common definition, map the infrastructure and think of ways to make it accessible. This process in itself has been very helpful. We do not talk necessarily about sharing all research infrastructure there is, but to apply the accessibility to some of infrastructure in a smart way - to attract people one wants. So it is important to take decisions of how to share and when to share. Also the question of funders role has to be explored, because the – EU, private founders make requirements and a new ways of thinking starts</p>

	<p>prevailing -have to facilitate sharing. We need to understand how to make it work, as we don't have same systems, protocols have to be established. So flexible models that respect national legislation, specific regulations have to be created and the culture of sharing should be enabled. Enablers should be detected and maximized</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achievements in Sharing Research Infrastructures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Research Infrastructures are strong drivers for the generation of research results and thus knowledge at European Universities.” • 4EU+ SwafS project TRAIN4EU+ has addressed transformation module 2 - "sharing research infrastructures" - within its Work package 3. • WP3 work on promising models for sharing infrastructures has led to a joint publication currently submitted to a journal. • Challenges in Sharing Research Infrastructures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • mapping research infrastructure and maintaining an up-to-date list • determine when and where sharing facilities “Core facilities” is the right solution • Ways forward in Sharing Research Infrastructures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are benefits from increased sharing of research infrastructures • There are good models on how to organize this. And some funding options are available. • But there is no simple way forward and there is no "one size fits all", also when it comes to sharing research infrastructures.
Speaker name (3):	Sven Idarand (Transform4Europe/T4ERI)
Summary of speaker content (3):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The SwafS programme project set the alliance quite an ambitious plans - the partners wanted to set joint agenda for collaboration (because until that time only few partners had done some standard research projects together). Therefore Transform4Europe wanted to make all the possible support structures to help the researchers find their own colleagues from different partners, so the collaboration platform was initiated that has now been launched to act as a matchmaking device. Experts in the fields were identified, having the authority within their institutions, to act as facilitators. • During the project Transform4Europe saw that the sharing of the infrastructure would be as important as the connection between the researchers, so we joined our infrastructure platform to the same system which would nurture the collaboration even more. • To foster even better collaboration between the partners Transform4Europe needed to see the human capital that each of the partners have. It was very important to give a voice in the development program for the research support staff (pointed out by EC as best practice). Although managing the piloting program for academic and administrative staff can be challenging, we see this a vital part of the future collaboration. • Transform4Europe has been very successful in building different structures, also in Open Science, Science Communication and PERI, but now the question is how can we carry out the actual actions, as changes take time to have any noticeable results. So we see our work

	<p>in the project as setting up an environment. Through the Science4All strategy, for example, we have planned a course on science communication for the researchers to build more on the universities' mission to serve the society as well, but the outcomes will be seen after the piloting phase.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While SwafS programme has given a real boost in the Transform4Europe alliance's activities in R&I, the program itself doesn't yet let us see the full effects of the started activities and the Erasmus+ program isn't so much meant to support R&I activities. Luckily a lot of activities developed in the T4ERI project also will continue in some form in our alliance's next phase funding from Erasmus+
Speaker name (4):	Laura Martin (SEA-EU/reSEArch EU)
Summary of speaker content (4):	<p>SEA-EU is specific in the sense that it consists of coastal European universities responding to society challenges of coastal cities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through the reSEArch-EU project, the SEA-EU alliance has worked towards intensifying and improving its research and innovation capacities through increased resilience (Anti-fragility think-tank), sustainable and open science practices, facilitation of innovation, engagement with stakeholders and long-term collaborations. • The most important challenge of the alliance has been to design and produce a Long Term Research Agenda, which has been built thanks to the analysis, the positioning of key investigators towards societal challenges and the evaluation of the common research activities, the research strengths of the alliance and the alignment of our research with the Agenda 2030 Goals, the European Research Missions and the Research Areas priorities of the Horizon Europe Programme. • The Long Term Research Agenda has been built thanks to the Governance documentation and good practices that have been reporting among the SEA EU Alliance such as: Position paper on reducing the carbon footprint of research activities, Strategies for stakeholder engagement, Joint SEA-EU Industrial PhD model recommendations, Report on best practices and learnings, workshops, mission-based hackathons, Policy paper with recommendations to fit regional priorities, Report in the best practices of cooperation within the socioeconomic, Report on gender, Digital transformation of research and innovation roadmap analysis, Advisory Board and Stakeholders Group report, SEA-EU Sustainable Development Goals Declaration, Report on Best Practices in Open Science, Industrial PhDs and life-long-learning, Survey report on doctoral students mobility; as well different SEA EU tools and initiatives as SEA-EU summer schools, SEA-EU Joint PhD, Blue Doctoral Community Alumni Network, etc. • Elaborating on the SEA-EU global vision, the alliance's vision and ambition for its research community is: (1) To be an international reference point recognised for excellence in research priority areas, a promoter of open and fair science as well as an exemplary model of research ethics and integrity, (2) To provide an internationally recognized environment for developing careers of young researchers, increase the integration within the alliance, provide seamless mobility and collaboration experiences. For each of the missions prioritised,

	specific objectives have been identified, several of which are cross-cutting.
Speaker name (5):	Nicole Birkle (FORTHEM/FIT FORTHEM)
Summary of speaker content (5):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The research dimension must be properly embedded in alliance actions, and that is why it needs funding. The SwafS call was highly appreciated, and we need to speak about how to continue from that, especially if we are asked to create as much synergies as possible with the education and outreach dimension. • The European Commission invited alliances to a dialogue about investment pathways promoting to using all the possibilities in the framework of Horizon Europe, e.g., MSCA, Infrastructures, the Widening Programme including Excellence Initiative, or other European funding schemes like Erasmus+, Digital Europe, National Support, and Structural funds. But there are issues with that approach, namely incompatibility between Swafs and these calls, constant need to apply and reapply, incompatible timeframes and priorities for various projects. • Bringing the member states on board: Alliances are constantly encouraged to lobby for future funding especially also for their research dimension on national level. Indeed, it is the responsibility of the participating universities to lobby regionally and nationally for robust co-funding of the alliances. FORTHEM is developing and refining respective concepts. However, it is important to note that not all Member States offer national co-financing at all, and that the regulations are so different that they hardly allow measures to be financed that benefit the entire alliance and that can be strategically deployed. • In order to be successful in the long term, alliances need a solid and stable basic funding we can build on to work on all missions. • FORTHEM tried to bring as much as possible what was created in FIT FORTHEM under the umbrella of the ERASMUS+ funded alliance structures in the second funding period, creating the Research, Innovation and Transfer Mission with three pillars: a mission board for strategic decisions, a joint virtual Research Services and Policy Office and a FORTHEM academy for Early-Stage Researchers.
Key discussion points & conclusions	<p>Question: EU will support projects not alliances, will there be an advantage if the project application comes from alliance? What will be the added value of project within the alliance?</p> <p>Lassen: I can tell from my experience - what vice rector can do- develop research infrastructure, common protocols, enable researchers work together, that will make application within alliance more attractive</p> <p>Nicole: we always suggest to add partners from the alliance, there is no no competition exchange, alliances are especially attractive for early stage researchers that need to establish networks. Established researchers step by step will see the advantages.</p> <p>Siobhan: some research teams already have track record for working together, interdisciplinarity comes with alliances, not competing but collaborating</p> <p>Katarzyna: trust has been built</p>

Annex 2: SwafS Forum 2023 Day 1 Workshop 2 – rapporteur summary

Day 1 Workshop 2 / 4eu+ speaker: CU Vice Rector Research Ladislav Kristoufek; moderator: 4eu+ policy officer Elena del Giorgio, UM.

Rapporteur name	Miriam Koktvedgaard Zeitzen
Rapporteur email	miriam.zeitzen@adm.ku.dk
Workshop name	Workshop 2: <i>Pilots and Action Plans: what are the SwafS projects leaving for future developments of the Alliances' R&I dimension</i>
Participants Name & role	Facilitator: Elena del Giorgio (4EU+) Rapporteur: Miriam Koktvedgaard Zeitzen (TRAIN4EU+ Project Manager) Speaker 1: Mattia Bellotti (EUTOPIA Secretary General) Speaker 2: Sigríður Beck (TRAIN EUTOPIA Management Board) Speaker 3: Sophia Karner (UNA.EUROPA Senior Policy Officer) Speaker 4: Manuel José Damásio (FILM-EU Coordinator) Speaker 5: Ladislav Kristoufek (4EU+ Vice Rector Research Charles University)
Topic 1 & discussion points	<p>a. Alliance speaker EUTOPIA: Mattia Bellotti, Secretary General & Sigríður Beck, TRAIN EUTOPIA Management Board</p> <p>b. Title of presentation <i>Common R&I Agenda: From conceptualisation and pilot in SwafS project to implementation at alliance level</i></p> <p>c. Summary of presentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ EUTOPIA is an alliance of 10 European universities that, working with a shared set of values and purpose, are developing long-term and sustainable collaboration across education, research, innovation, and service to society. ➤ Through the SwafS project EUTOPIA TRAIN, EUTOPIA partner universities have developed a common R&I Agenda, outlining the priorities and principles to achieve two main objectives: i) developing and strengthening collaboration to promote knowledge sharing, excellence, and societal impact, and ii) fostering a culture of innovation and continuous improvement to drive societal impact. ➤ The common R&I agenda also defines a set of activities to implement to achieve the objectives, including activities that have been piloted during the SwafS project (EUTOPIA TRAIN) and, in some cases, continued through the core Erasmus+ project (EUTOPIA MORE). ➤ The presentation will illustrate the strategy followed by EUTOPIA universities to successfully move from conceptualisation to piloting and consolidation of these activities, while also highlighting the challenges that are still ahead. <p>d. Question for discussion <i>“How can Alliances effectively balance strategic expectations about enhancing R&I collaborations across universities with actual needs and capacities for institutional transformation? What are the lessons learnt and perspectives for the future?”</i></p>
Topic 2 & discussion points	<p>a. Alliance speaker UNA.EUROPA: Sophia Karner, Senior Policy Officer</p> <p>b. Title of presentation <i>Una Europa’s vision for research & innovation</i></p>

	<p>c. Summary of presentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Who is Una Europa (our journey so far) ➤ Una Europa 2030 Strategy: holistic framework for collaboration for the decade ahead across three main pillars (Powering the Research of the Future; Pioneering the Education of the Future; Shaping the Society of the Future) ➤ Una Europa Vision for Research & Innovation (diving into Pillar I) to advance transnational research collaborations, and to do so across disciplinary and institutional borders, this vision focuses on three key ambitions (informed by results of the Una.Resin project). Each ambition to be illustrated with concrete example. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Supporting the Development of Interdisciplinary Hubs for Research, Education and Knowledge Transfer ○ Providing a transnational framework for training early career researchers ○ Opening up research and data infrastructures and resources ➤ What's next for Una Europa? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Una Europa matrix exercise, which has been designed to encourage prioritization exercise at the highest decision-making levels of the alliance, proposing concrete activities (matching ambitions and investment needs) ○ Importance of support structures going forward, i.e. Una Europa Clusters ○ Reflections on future investment and policy needs <p>d. Question for discussion</p> <p><i>“From your perspective, what support do European University Alliances need to take their research & innovation dimension to the next level? How can we match ambitions and investment needs going forward?”</i></p>
<p>Topic 3 & discussion points</p>	<p>a. Alliance speaker FILM-EU: Manuel José Damásio, Coordinator</p> <p>b. Title of presentation <i>Jointly designing a research agenda through joint research initiatives: the FilmEU Artistic research Agenda</i></p> <p>c. Summary of presentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ FilmEU grounded the development of its joint research agenda around the concept of artistic research and the development of joint dynamic clusters that, fueled by an original seed funding program, infuse a community of researchers and increase the Alliance R&I capacity. ➤ The presentation will describe this process, lessons learned and foreseen next stages in implementing this transformational joint research agenda. <p>d. Question for discussion</p> <p><i>“Considering the diverse profiles of our Alliances, especially in terms of thematic focus or size, how have collaborations in the R&I dimension shaped? What are the commonalities and differences in cooperation models and needs?”</i></p>
<p>Topic 4 & discussion points</p>	<p>a. Alliance speaker 4eu+: Ladislav Kristoufek, Vice-Rector Research Charles University, Prague</p> <p>b. Title of presentation <i>Unleashing Potential: Exploring the Dynamic Synergies Between Education and R&I in 4EU+</i></p>

	<p>c. Summary of presentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 4eu+ initiatives to boost R&I dimensions as well as synergies between research and education include minigrants, SEED4eu+ calls and visiting professorship calls; joint doctoral training is also in the works in 4eu+ ➤ Best practices and challenges in creating synergies internally to partner institutions (especially in large universities often different divisions managing education and R&I) and to Alliances (alignment between Erasmus+ projects and SwafS/R&I dimension in terms of timing and type of financial support); ➤ Best practices and challenges in the interplay with associated partners and stakeholders in the ecosystems. <p>d. Question for discussion</p> <p><i>“How have Alliances built synergies between the education and R&I dimensions? What opportunities and challenges have been encountered and how can we further strengthen connections across dimensions?”</i></p>
<p>Key conclusions</p>	<p>Moderator: introduction & policy context</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SwafS projects laid the ground for institutional transformations • Change of policy landscape in-between: launch of Horizon Europe in 2021 and launch of the ERA Policy Agenda with many actions that mirror the transformational activities taking place in SwafS projects (action 3, 8, 13 and 17) • SwafS projects have provided policy feedback during the project lifetime • The number of Alliances have grown with repercussions at national level. As the number of universities involved grew, the capacity of some MS to directly fund them decreases <p>EUTOPIA: Top-down strategic development vis-à-vis bottom-up implementation – Embedding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EUTOPIA has 4 global partners, special feature • Young Leaders Academy: Early-career researchers focus • GLENN Office: grants office. Through the support of research you can get excellent research and impact • R&I Atlas: map of existing mobility programmes across universities • Connected research communities: bottom-up call to create networks of researchers focusing on activities related to global challenges • 2024-2026 R&I Agenda: Enhance capacity building through collaboration; Early career researchers is the target group • Main challenges: ownership, organization and responsibility, funding for consolidation, prioritization between activities, evaluation of the results and impact • How to manage expectations at institutional level (from the communities but also from funders)? We need to be pragmatic and not haste. With more strategic thinking we could have chosen to streamline actions that were more important to us <p>UNA.EUROPA: Investment pathways (EU and national levels)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU funding in different programmes; member states funding and commitment; regulatory frameworks hampering or facilitating cooperation; type of incentives for researchers to foster R&I collaborations. • R&I Strategy: a) Developing interdisciplinary hubs for research, education and knowledge transfer; b) Providing a transnational framework for early-career researchers: joint doctoral programmes and more joint training

	<p>opportunities; c) Opening up research and data infrastructures and resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey in 2023 about expectations on the Alliance that will inform the future Action plan starting from 2024 • Clusters of professionals linked to the SwafS: how to continue them outside the SwafS they were born in? • MS should co-invest • Need to be more clear about the clear added-value of research alliances compared to other alliances • What is the impact outside our Alliance? • What makes Alliances unique is joint structures and having a space for bottom-up collaboration and interdisciplinarity for researchers • The ERA Agenda should come with funding; We need funding to implement the ambitions. We need funding to meet all the missions of universities • Some SwafS stretched too much on different actions: it would have been impossible to focus on them all <p>FILM-EU: Alliances profile and models for cooperation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alliances have different profiles: some more thematically oriented (polytechnics; business schools/social sciences, arts etc), others composed by multidisciplinary universities; some have enlarged, others are smaller; some have placed a greater focus on one mission (i.e. education), others (also) on other missions. • EC mentions a lot different models for cooperation and different solutions are being developed in terms of Alliances governance, services that are being developed • Use of pilots as drivers of a joint R&I agenda • Matchmaking process among institutions (from 4 to 8) • Starting from artistic research to get to societal challenges • Creation of formal groups of researchers • Challenges: Contractual dilemmas; Connections and funding: increase to attract funding thanks to the creation of the Film-EU Alliance; Needed instruments to continue • Recruiting research managers is key, specifically for non research intensive institutions • Bring together researchers can allow them to attract external funding • Alignment of the Alliances with Smart Specialisation Strategies • Challenges of national contexts in terms of HR (hiring, retaining talents, etc.) • Funding: conceptualisation worked but then the continuation of activities in SwafS is now up to internal university budgets which will limit the development further • Legal entity can be a challenge or an opportunity <p>4eu+: Synergies between education and R&I</p> <p>Discussion with CHARM-EU, ERUA, UNIVERSEH, ENGAGE-EU</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional development and training is included in other Alliances new Erasmus projects: Open Science, civil engagement, gender, diversity, etc. all the streams from the SwafS will form part of the professional development programme > How to motivate people to get courses done? • Database of experts
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same Academic Council for research and education • Matchmaking events: 4 projects came out of it but no funding received > 4EU+ also organised a match-making event. Difficult to measure the impact • Autonomy self-study courses on Open Science • Similar to 4EU+ courses> Online student portal; Student portal with all the courses. Very popular • There is a problem of research funding for research itself; Engagement of Faculties is important; Challenge: involvement of all researchers • Education and research have to be conducted together • Pay Master students to have exchanges (in France it is mandatory) > involvement of students in Seed4EU (4EU+) • Teaching through research activities: putting researchers together and see how they can teach together
<p>Recommended next actions if applicable.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build on the SwafS projects' efforts to position European University Alliances as key contributors to the European R&I landscape, highlighting their unique value in complement to existing R&I collaborations. • Advocate for future investment needs to allow European University Alliances to take forward their ambitions and fulfil their potential as drivers of the European Research Area, in Europe as well as globally. • Research Support Offices have a clear role in steering a lot of challenges of the Alliances; fx. when some universities outsource proposal writing to external consultants • Research Management should be a priority for future funding. That will help to operationalise many of the activities of the SwafS • How can we respond to the multiple challenges that Europe faces today? Some universities are trying to focus on challenges.

